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Electric and thermal efficiency improvement by steam pressure optimization in a dual-pressure HRSG

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Introduction

In past years, development in combined heat and power production technology led to increasing number of modern CHP industrial applications [1-5], such as combustion engines and gas turbines in combined cycles [6-7]. The use of advanced materials and sophisticated design allowed especially GTCC (gas turbine combined cycles) to manifest their supremacy in electrical efficiency among the well established CHP applications. Electrical efficiency up to 60 % in commercial application [3,8] was reported, with the prospect of further increase towards 65 % [9]. Thus, in the next years, GTCC probably will continue to be a very flexible way to produce both heat and power either in base load or peak load shaving operations [7, 10-12] at relatively low investment cost compared to other applications (especially fuel cells) [13-18] which haven't yet penetrated the market sufficiently to become a serious competitor to the GTCC, especially at large scale applications.

Research on gas turbines and topping cycle generally is directed mainly to development of special materials for turbine blades, in order to withstand temperatures above currently adopted 1400 °C [9,19] as well as to replace air cooling [10] of the blades by steam cooling [19] and/or to reduce the amount of air needed to be bled from compressor exit to cool the blades [20]. Inlet air cooling [7], compressor air intercooling [9-12], flue gas reheat [19], air bottoming cycle (ABC) [21,22], humid air turbine (HAT) [23], steam injections (STIG) [6,7,12], heat recuperation and chemical recuperation [6,9,24] are other options that either already are commercially available or are under development. New concepts are needed as well to reduce NO_x formation reflecting more stringent limits for emissions; especially because NO_x are prone to form at high temperatures.

Heat recovery steam generator is a well-proven concept to convert waste heat of turbine flue gases, which other ways would be lost, into useful heat in steam. While only single-pressure design was used in past, recent applications adopt either two- or three-pressure design [7-9,11,25] with steam superheat and reheat [26] to both increase the heat recovery efficiency and to boost steam bottoming cycle efficiency. Because of relatively low flue gas temperature (400 to 600 °C according to turbine type) at the HRSG inlet and their low emission level, ordinary materials are used for construction. Nowadays, there is practically no intense research on HRSGs, since it is a well established technology and it depends on application and specific requests of customers, which design to choose.

Nevertheless, there still are possibilities how to improve both thermal and electric efficiency, especially by pinch and steam pressure and temperature optimization [7-9]. It usually should be carried out by the producer, but it has been shown that even the well known CCGT producers like Siemens and ABB Alstom don't really exploit these possibilities by choosing too large pinch (8 to

15 K) and by choosing established steam pressure ratios rather than optimal ones [8]. Thus, in a retrofit, one still can achieve interesting efficiency increase just by optimizing steam pressure levels [25] – pinch value is connected with heat transfer intensity and with heat exchange surface and steam temperature is often limited either by HRSG construction material or steam turbine upper limit for inlet steam temperature.

Steam pressure levels retrofit

Prior to retrofitting an existing multi-pressure HRSG, one has to collect enough data describing the studied system. Usually, not all the required data are measured and the task is to calculate them from other available system performance data, using material and energy balances. Double-checking of measured mass flows is always recommended. Data needed to perform the retrofit are as follows: gas turbine flue gas temperature, stack temperature, pressure and temperature and mass flows of each steam produced, boiler feed water temperature, HRSG arrangement and the range of possible pressures, temperatures and mass flows which the steam turbine would accept. Auxiliary data which might be used but don't affect the calculation accuracy seriously are boiler blow down rate and steam pressure drop in superheaters.

Enthalpies and mass flows in each HRSG component must fulfill mass and energy conservation principle, thus unknown flue gas and steam temperatures can be calculated at the inlet and outlet of each HRSG component. The obtained temperatures together with mass flows are further used to calculate logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD) for each component and subsequently to obtain U.A values from the combined energy balance and heat transfer equation:

$$Q = U.A.LMTD = m.c_p.\Delta t \quad (1)$$

A set of U.A values should be obtained for a couple of CCGT full load as well as part load operations. A set of $m.c_p$ values for flue gas is valuable as well and will be used in next step. As a next step, one chooses other intermediate pressure steam pressure (and proximate superheat temperature) and iteratively calculates backwards the new steam mass flow rates, under the constraint of fulfilling all mass and energy balances as well as of arriving at the same U.A values as before. Of course, U.A values might change when changing steam mass flow and parameters, however they are assumed constant for a given CCGT load for simplicity.

Next part of retrofit is to check steam turbine characteristics and correction graphs, as to learn the effect of changed steam parameters and mass flows on steam turbine output. Consequently, new steam turbine output is calculated and compared with the old one. Result of the calculation is either CCGT output loss or gain for a given fuel amount consumed.

Composite curve [27] is a very useful graphical tool for retrofit, since it immediately reveals violation of constraints mentioned above. An example of a typical composite curve for a HRSG is given in **Fig. 1**, where flue gas and steam temperatures are plotted as a function of heat absorption from flue gases. In fact, it is a heat exchanger temperature profile. Instead of heat absorption, amount of exchanged heat can be used to draw composite curves. In each point of the chart, a certain temperature difference must exist between the hot stream (flue gases) and the cold stream (steam) as to ensure heat transfer. Energy balance and heat transfer equation violation results in crossing of hot stream and cold stream curves, which is physically impossible. Pinch point is the least temperature difference of hot and cold stream in the whole HRSG; it is located in the HP evaporator, as to ensure as big HP steam mass flow as possible, since HP steam is more valuable for electricity production than IP or LP steam. The lower the pinch point value, the better the heat recovery from the flue gas, but the larger heat transfer areas needed. In each situation, there exists an economical tradeoff between heat recovery and HRSG component cost.

Fig. 1 A typical composite curve of a dual-pressure HRSG [7]

Case study

As an object of our study, we chose a newly built CCGT in Slovakia, comprising two aeroderivative 32 MW gas turbines, two dual-pressure HRSGs and a 20 MW induction condensing steam turbine with one extraction for feed water heating and deaeration and for heat supply into the nearby town. Important parameters are given below in **Tab. 1** and a schematic view of CCGT is given in **Fig. 2**.

Fig. 2 Scheme of studied CCGT plant

Fuel	Nominal power output, MW _{el}	Nominal electric efficiency, %	High pressure steam pressure, MPa and temperature, °C	Intermediate pressure steam pressure, MPa and temperature, °C	Extraction pressure, MPa	Dry condenser pressure, MPa
Natural gas, LHV 34,3 MJ/Nm ³	80	50	6,2/440	1,3/255	0,37	0,012

Tab. 1 Nominal CCGT performance parameters

Each of the HRSGs has beside the steam generating sections one hot pressurized water section, which, at the moment, is idle, but it is activate during heating season. Flue gas temperature varies with load from 400 to 500 °C and stack temperature is quite stable around 155 °C in the off-heating mode.

Composite curve of studied system at full load operation is shown in **Fig. 3**. As can be seen, pinch values are of order of some few Kelvins, which is very favorable for extensive heat recovery from the flue gas. As usual, LMTD is highest in HP superheater and HP evaporator, which reduces the heat exchange surface needed.

Fig. 3 Composite curve of studied system at full load

Fig. 4 shows obtained U.A values for HP and IP sections as a function of steam generation rate. Increase of U.A, thus of overall heat transfer coefficients (since A is constant) is well documented. In case of economizers it is well explained by increasing velocities on flue gas as well as on steam side, which reduces thermal resistances on both heat exchanger sides. Considering the evaporators, the increase may be not so apparent, but the situation here is a bit more complicated. Both HP and IP evaporators are natural circulation, drum – type, where the driving force for circulation is density difference between the just boiling water coming down the water tubes and the water-vapor mixture rising up the tubes on the other side of HRSG. Heat transfer and circulation

velocity are strongly bound together and overall heat transfer coefficients in evaporators can, unlike in economizers, reach some maximal value.

Fig. 4 U.A values for HRSG sections as a function of steam generation rate, Legend: solid diamond – IP Eco, solid triangle – IP Evap., solid square – HP EcoI, open square – HP EcoII, open triangle – HP Evap.

Results and discussion

Fig. 5 HRSG composite curve at full load after P_{IP} reduction from 1,3 MPa to 0,7 MPa

After calculating U.A values, optimization was started. Optimal value found for IP pressure is 0,7 MPa, which nearly is the lower limit of acceptable IP steam pressures by the induction turbine.

Since the pressure of HP steam is 6,2 MPa, it corresponds with the rule of thumb establishing the optimal value for HP and IP pressure ratio for a dual-pressure HRSG as $P_{HP}/P_{IP} \sim 10/1$ [5]. **Fig. 5** shows the corresponding composite curve at CCGT full load.

When compared with **Fig. 3**, **Fig. 5** shows increased heat load at HP EcoII, whereas that at HP EcoI decreased. This can be explained by the fact, that after decreasing the IP steam evaporation temperature by 20 °C (pressure decrease from 1,3 to 0,7 MPa), the system had to adjust itself to new situation, which means decrease of outlet water temperature in EcoI. The same is valid for IP Eco. IP evaporator also shows increased heat load, which from the great part is due to increased IP steam generation and from the small part due to the increase of latent heat of evaporation due to evaporating pressure decrease. Important data about system performance before and after P_{IP} decrease are summed up in **Tab. 2 a,b**.

Parameter	Heat input in natural gas, MW	Stack temperature, °C	Heat recovered in HRSG, MW	HP steam mass flow, t/h
Before	80,9	152,9	33,8	36,5
After	80,9	142,0	34,9	36,2
Difference	0	- 10,9	+ 1,1	- 0,3
Parameter	IP steam mass flow rate, t/h	Steam turbine output, MW _e	Thermal efficiency of HRSG, %	Electric efficiency of CCGT, %
Before	6,9	8,59	66,46	47,70
After	8,7	8,75	68,63	47,89
Difference	+ 1,8	+ 0,16	+ 2,17	+ 0,19

Tab. 2 a Performance parameters of CCGT before and after IP steam pressure reduction at one gas turbine full load (30 MW_e) and the other one turned off.

Parameter	Heat input in natural gas, MW	Stack temperature, °C	Heat recovered in HRSGs, MW	HP steam mass flow, t/h
Before	130,6	153,5	56,4	60,0
After	130,6	142,0	58,9	59,3
Difference	0	- 13,5	+ 2,5	- 0,7
Parameter	IP steam mass flow rate, t/h	Steam turbine output, MW _e	Thermal efficiency of HRSGs, %	Electric efficiency of CCGT, %
Before	12,9	16,33	66,28	47,11
After	16,5	16,62	69,0	47,34
Difference	+ 3,6	+ 0,29	+ 2,71	+ 0,23

Tab. 2 b Performance parameters of CCGT before and after IP steam pressure reduction at both gas turbines operating at 22,6 MW_e.

Tab. 2 a,b show the surplus in heat recovered in HRSGs, in steam turbine output and subsequently in thermal efficiency of HRSGs and electric efficiency of the whole CCGT. It is possible to recover up to 2,5 MW of heat more than before P_{IP} reduction, which leads to steam turbine output increase by up to 300 kW_e. This figure may not appear impressive, but when

considered that the intermediate pressure steam, according to the steam turbine characteristics, contributes to power generation only by less than 2 MW_e, on that basis is the surplus of 300 kW_e more than 15 % increase! The surplus of 300 kW_e further enables the CCGT reduction of fuel costs and of CO₂ emissions on the yearly basis by more than 760 t CO₂ while keeping the amount of electrical energy produced the same. Such amount of CO₂ is usually released by the studied CCGT by operating more than 40 hours at average load.

Conclusions

A newly built CCGT was studied and subjected to steam pressure optimization in order to increase both thermal and electric efficiency of the whole CCGT. Retrofit computation was based on combining energy balances and heat transfer equations. For graphical demonstration of computation, composite curves were constructed and analyzed. U.A values were assumed independent on intermediate steam pressure and this simplification served well in iterative computations. It has been shown that a potential for electric output increase by 300 kW_e exists, increasing the CCGT overall electric efficiency by 0,24 %, which on the basis of intermediate pressure electric output is a more than 15 % increase. This measure enables the CCGT to decrease the fuel costs as well as to decrease the CO₂ emissions.

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